

STUDY OF HARDENING METHODS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Increasing the child's body's resistance to adverse environmental factors significantly reduces the incidence of diseases, because hardened children are not afraid of strong winds, temperature changes, or hypothermia. Hardening greatly improves the work of internal organs, promotes muscle development, activates metabolic processes, strengthens the nervous system. The study of methods of hardening children improves their immune system, the body's fight and increases.*

Keywords: *hardening, clean air, water hardening, physical activity, daily routine.*

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ МЕТОДОВ ЗАКАЛИВАНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *Повышение устойчивости детского организма к неблагоприятным факторам внешней среды значительно снижает заболеваемость, ведь закаленные дети не боятся сильного ветра, перепадов температуры, переохлаждения. Закаливание значительно улучшает работу внутренних органов, способствует развитию мышц, активизирует обменные процессы, укрепляет нервную систему. Изучение методов закаливания детей повышает их иммунную систему, сопротивляемость организма и повышает.*

Ключевые слова: *закаливание, чистый воздух, водное закаливание, двигательная активность, режим дня.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, preschool education has been paying great attention to the improvement of preschool children, since the health of children is directly related to the well-being of our society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Statistics on the health status of young children today do not allow us to be optimistic about the future. If you do not pay due attention to the health of children, then the incidence will only increase with age. Therefore, I decided to pay attention - hardening. In our second younger group (children 3-4 years old), the daily routine is aimed at hardening the child's body and wellness work is underway. The morning begins with gymnastics. It is important for hardening the body, improving the performance of children after sleep and regular physical training in order to improve the muscular apparatus, cardiovascular and respiratory systems. We organize a walk 2 times a day: in the morning - before lunch and in the afternoon - after a nap or before the children go home. Walking is a powerful way to harden the body. When dressing for a walk, we make sure that the children do not put on a lot of things. Dressing for classes also helps to harden the body, as it gets an air bath for a while. After a nap, we perform awakening exercises. This contributes to the hardening of the body. The gymnastics of waking up in the crib, includes the gradual awakening of the child and exercises for various muscle groups. I start doing gymnastics with the awakened children, the others join as they wake up. The teacher wakes up each child individually, gently stroking, and then we perform 3-4 exercises. This creates a gradual smooth transition from sleep to wakefulness. The main rule is the exclusion of sudden movements that

can cause muscle strain, overexcitation. The duration of gymnastics in bed is 2-3 minutes. Then the children proceed to perform a set of breathing exercises, which is very important for the prevention of colds and diseases of the upper respiratory tract. Breathing exercises strengthen the respiratory muscles, improve blood circulation in the upper respiratory tract and increase resistance to colds, as well as endurance during physical exertion. The point is to perform a set of exercises with the nose. In order to evoke an emotional response in children, as well as a desire to perform exercises together with a teacher, I use game exercises, accompanying them with various verses. Then the children switch to walking barefoot, walking along the paths of "Health". Health trails are a good helper in wellness work. It is known that there are many active points on the feet that stimulate them, we have a positive effect on the processes taking place in the body. When walking barefoot on the "path of health", we perform a kind of foot massage and thereby tone the whole body. The meaning of walking barefoot is the hardening of the skin of the feet, which occurs mainly under the influence of low floor temperatures. Next, we do exercises. Walking, jumping, inclines depending on the complex. The exercises are also scheduled for 2-3 minutes. The total difficulty is 5-7 minutes. At the end, we will definitely do an exercise to restore breathing. Physical education classes are also held with children twice a week. Children perform water procedures with great pleasure. First, wash the face, hands, then hands to the elbow, and then to the shoulder joint. Wet wiping of the chest and abdomen is carried out. It should be noted that during the entire health-improving game hour, the air is tempered. Getting out of bed, the child receives a contrast-air bath. The process of moving the child from the bedroom to the group, to the bathroom, back to the group. Thus, there is a change in the temperature regime, which is also a strengthening factor. It is important that the duration of hardening procedures is no more than 20 minutes. Proper hardening of the body can give a positive result only if the following principles are observed: The effect of an irritating factor on the body should be gradual. This principle is very important, since the child's body does not offer much resistance and the use of strong stimuli without preliminary gradual preparation can lead to negative results. Hardening of children will give the best result if a strict dosage and a gradual increase in irritation are established. It is best to start hardening in the warm season. For example, the gradual lightening of clothes in spring, a gradual decrease in temperature during water procedures, a gradual increase in the duration of sunbathing, etc.

RESULTS

The sequence of application of hardening procedures. First, air baths should be carried out, and then you can move on to water and solar. It is necessary to combine tempering activities with physical activity of children, gymnastic exercises, staying in the fresh air, observing the daily routine. You can start hardening from the age of two weeks after the child is examined by a pediatrician and the approval of wellness procedures on his part. In order for a good undertaking to really benefit, parents should adhere to a number of rules:

- You need to temper the baby all year round – there should be no breaks, and the intensity and duration of hardening procedures should be gradually increased.
- Regularity of procedures is the key to successful hardening. If you do them "once from time to time", then you should hardly expect positive results.

- Try to carry out all procedures in the form of a game. The hardening effect will only increase if the baby likes this process. Adopt everything that your baby loves – toys, poems, songs, pictures. Improvise so that the baby is fun and interesting.
- It is recommended to combine hardening with massage, so the development of the child will be harmonious, and well-being is good.
- According to medical statistics, children who are tempered by their parents have stronger immunity and are about 3.5 times less ill with acute respiratory diseases than their untreated peers.

DISCUSSION

In any case, do not allow the child to overheat or hypothermia during the procedures. Thermoregulation in babies is still imperfect, and fluctuations in body temperature are the norm for them. But after all, hardening should in no case go to harm! Therefore, carefully monitor the temperature of the air and water, do not overdo it with the baby's stay in the sun. Always choose clothes and shoes suitable for the weather for the child and protect his head from the sun. It should be noted that when quenching, the following conditions must be observed: Regularity. Only this can ensure a certain success. At the same time, you need to start with a conversation with your parents – they should maintain the effect at home. Be sure to take into account the well-being and emotional state of the child. The child should feel comfortable, not be afraid, not cry (in order to avoid a negative reaction, hardening procedures for children should take place in a playful way) and at the same time be healthy.

CONCLUSIONS

All activities carried out in kindergarten are impossible without the participation of the family in this process, since a number of entertainment activities must be continued at home. The participation of parents is very important in all the work of the preschool institution. We have designed stands for parents in groups, regularly hold consultations and parent meetings. After all, it is only through the joint activities of teachers and parents that the most significant results can be achieved in solving the problem - reducing the incidence of children, strengthening their health.

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